

Slope stability of deep surface coal mines in the presence of a weak zone

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Abstract:

Coal and lignite (brown coal) are geo-resources that have been governing energy production for decades. Geomechanical challenges, particularly slope stability, related to surface coal and lignite mines are critical during operation and will also determine the post-coal era for these areas. Several failure incidents (landslides) have been reported in mining areas, typically associated with a sub-horizontal failure surface on a weak - clay or marl - layer or an interface of low strength. This weak zone controls the soil profile in terms of stability and is common in several mines globally. In this work, this soil profile is analysed in terms of slope stability through the probability of slope failure; such a systematic analysis is currently missing from the literature. Initially, several numerical issues are addressed in the simulation of the problem. Moreover, the essential parameters' effect is examined: the height and the inclination of the slope, the inclination, thickness, and strength of the weak zone, and the strength of the overburden soil. Their effect on slope stability is evaluated by combining the probabilistic point estimate method with the finite element method and the shear strength reduction technique. This work can support a preliminary slope stability analysis and expands the knowledge and understanding of slope stability of a weak zone soil profile. It is concluded that in the presence of a weak zone, the inclination and strength of the weak zone and the water conditions are the most critical parameters and control the stability.

Article highlights

- Slope stability is performed on a soil profile with a weak zone, describing a common type of coal mines' failure in several countries.
- Numerical issues of practical importance are addressed on the simulation and analysis of the problem.
- The inclination and shear strength of the weak zone together with the water conditions control the stability of the mines' slopes.

Keywords: residual strength, lignite mining, finite element method, shear strength reduction technique, point estimate method, probability of failure

1. Introduction

Coal and lignite mining are geo-resources that have significantly contributed to the global energy needs during several decades, accounting for 25% of the global energy production in 2000, 30% in 2010 and 27% in 2019 (BP 2020). In 2019, approximately 8 billion metric tons of coal and lignite were produced worldwide (Enerdata 2020). When the coal deposits are located relatively near the surface, their cost-efficient extraction is usually achieved by surface, open-pit (also called opencast) mining methods. The sustainability of such mines is significantly affected by the stability of the corresponding excavations. Several slope failure events in open-pit lignite and coal mines have been reported in the past (e.g. Prountzopoulos et al. 2017; Solak et al. 2017; Zevgolis et al. 2019; Zhigang et al. 2020); such incidents set at risk human lives, infrastructure, and mining operation. Additionally, landslides pose a severe risk to the reclamation of mining areas. So, even though several countries worldwide have pledged to cease any lignite or coal-related activities soon (e.g. Canada, Germany, France, Italy, the United Kingdom and Greece), slope stability of the existing mining areas will still be of importance in the forthcoming period.

Stability failure mechanisms are often associated with a horizontal or sub-horizontal failure surface developing on a low strength zone, usually located near the bottom of the excavation (Zevgolis et al. 2019). This zone can be a layer or an interface between layers of low shear strength, hereafter named as the weak zone. As a result, a circular type of failure does not represent the failure surface (e.g. Kavvadas et al. 2020; Leonardos 2004), but a composite failure mechanism is observed, with sliding occurring along the weak zone and reaching the top of the slope with a planar or curvilinear transition. This mechanism is dominated by the weak zone's residual strength due to the immense shear strains developed on the relatively thin interface during ground movements. This type of failure is encountered in open-pit coal

and lignite mining in several countries, such as Greece (Kavvadas et al. 2020; Leonardos 2004; Zevgolis et al. 2019), Turkey (e.g. Ulusay et al. 2014; Ulusay et al. 2001; Ural and Yuksel 2004), Poland (e.g. Bednarczyk 2017), Czech Republic (e.g. Mencil 1977), and Australia (e.g. Ghadrhan et al. 2020; McQuillan et al. 2018). The weak zone mechanism is widespread in several landslide phenomena and several lignite and coal mines' slope failure events globally.

Failure incidents related to a weak zone (also named a weak layer) have been discussed and studied by several researchers outside the context of mining (e.g. Bromhead 1992; Urciuoli et al. 2007). Landslides governed by such failure mechanisms have been globally documented, e.g. in Canada, Hong Kong, Scandinavia, Spain and the United Kingdom (L'Heureux et al. 2012; Lastras et al. 2004; Puzrin et al. 2017; Quinn 2009; Zhang and Wang 2020). In these cases, various reasons may have triggered the reported incidents, such as the removal of the downslope support due to soil degradation, or a local increase of the pore water pressures due to seismic loading, or gas hydrate disassociation. Nevertheless, the failure surface's non-circular shape and the weak zone's importance are two features that remain alike for all these events.

Different approaches have been investigated towards the design and prevention of such stability issues. Huang (1983) has discussed this failure mechanism and proposed an analytical approach based on limit equilibrium analysis to assess the Safety Factor (SF). Kavvadas et al. (2020) also developed a simplified analytical model for Greek lignite mines and investigated the importance of critical parameters on the SF of mining slopes. However, the limitations of the analytical models and the increase of the computational power during the last decades have made numerical analysis the primary tool for stability evaluation of open-pit mining (e.g. Cała et al. 2020; Ozbay and Cabalar 2015; Steiakakis et al. 2004). The weak zone's importance is discussed in many studies, but its effect on stability has not been rigorously examined. In

most cases, numerical modelling is performed for back analysis of slope failures, assessing the weak zone's strength parameters (e.g. Tutluoglu et al. 2011).

The present study fills the gap of systematic numerical analysis on the slope stability of deep surface excavations in the presence of a weak zone, typically encountered in open-pit lignite and coal mines. It contributes to the understanding and quantification of the effect of various parameters on the failure mechanism controlled by a weak zone.

The finite element method is primarily employed, combined with the shear strength reduction technique to calculate the SF. Additionally, the point estimate method was used to estimate the statistical moments of the SF and the probability of slope failure. Several researchers have combined probabilistic methods with finite elements to evaluate slopes' reliability (e.g. Griffiths and Fenton 2004). Through this framework, the critical geotechnical parameters' uncertainty can be considered and involved in the analysis quantitatively. Moreover, the probability of failure provides a more rational assessment of the risks associated with slope stability than the SF. It also quantifies better the slope stability than the SF: differences in the probability of slope failure quantify actual different risk levels. On the contrary, Safety Factor works in principle qualitatively in terms of risk evaluation: low SFs ("relatively" close to 1) denote possible failure and high SFs safety.

Initially, the critical parameters that govern the failure mechanism are identified based on the literature and experience from Greek lignite surface mines. Two finite element (Plaxis2D and RS2) and one limit equilibrium (Slide2) geotechnical software are implemented to compare the SF calculation. Additionally, slopes with benches, as in engineering practice, and without benches, as in slope stability analysis and design, are compared.

The central part of this work includes evaluating the effect of the geometrical and geotechnical parameters and pore water pressures on the slope stability of mines. Overall,

the present analysis on the influence of the critical parameters on the stability allows for the preliminary stability evaluation of a lignite/coal mine and the appropriate quantification of each parameter's effect through the probability of slope failure.

2. Development of the reference model

2.1. Soil stratigraphy and properties

Figure 1 illustrates a characteristic geometry with the weak zone crossing at the bottom of the excavation, lying above the bedrock and below the overburden soil. In practice, the prevalent weak zone can be found close to the toe, but sometimes also below or above the bottom of the excavation. Herein, the weak zone is assumed to cross the slope's surface at the toe of the slope (i.e. at the bottom of the excavation) as this is most critical for stability analysis. Suppose the failure surface crosses the stratigraphy beneath the excavation's bottom; in that case, the failure surface should resurface on the bottom, thus, passing twice through the non-weak soil of higher strength. In contrast, a failure surface above the excavation could be interpreted as an equivalent slope of smaller height; thus, higher SF is expected, as will also be shown in the sequel.

Figure 1. Simplified stratigraphy of a surface coal mine slope with a weak zone at the bottom of the excavation

The overburden soil consists of layers of sterile materials (for instance, in Greek lignite mines, these are mostly stiff to hard clays and marls) and lignite seams. As shown in the sequel, the overburden soil's properties are less crucial than the properties of the weak zone. Additionally, these layers could be characterised for slope stability in terms of their shear strength only, and they frequently have similar shear strength. As a result, the overburden soil will be simulated as a homogeneous material (Figure 1). At the bottom of the excavation, a bedrock formation with high strength and stiffness is commonly encountered. This region (underneath the weak zone) does not directly contribute to the slope stability analysis if a weak zone is present.

Geometry and soil properties critically affect the stability of the slope. Geometrical and geotechnical parameters that are expected to be important are the height (H) and the inclination (β) of the slope, the inclination (β_z) and thickness (d_z) of the weak zone, and the soil's strength for both the overburden soil (ϕ , c) and the weak zone (ϕ_z , c_z). Slope stability literature recurrently discusses the effect of the parameters H , β , ϕ and c (e.g. Rahardjo et al. 2007). Leonardos (2004) identified the parameters of the weak zone (β_z , ϕ_z and c_z) as critical, and Kavvadas et al. (2020) tentatively analysed them for Greek lignite surface mines, based on a simple analytical model.

During the last decades, excavations have become exceptionally large and, on occasions, up to 200m deep. Slope inclination may vary in a wide range, depending on the exploitation method and the mechanical characteristics of the soils. Large bucket-wheel excavators are usually employed to exploit such deep excavations, forming slopes with inclinations 1:7-1:4 (8° - 14°) for the mines' sustainable operation (Kavvadas et al. 2020). Regarding the weak zone geometry, its thickness varies between a few millimetres and several tens of centimetres. At the same time, its inclination may differ from the horizontal up to 6° , based on reported failure incidents (e.g. Kavvadas et al. 2013; Steiakakis et al. 2018).

In a recent research study, Theocharis et al. (2021) organised and presented a large geotechnical database collected from various boreholes in several Greek lignite mines. Extensive laboratory results, including index and classification properties, triaxial, ring shear and direct shear tests, were statistically analysed. The authors reported that fine-grained soils dominate Greek lignite mines, and shear strength parameters (friction angle and cohesion) of the overburden soil formations often vary in a narrow range. In that vein, considering the overburden soil formations as a single material for slope stability analyses is a reasonable assumption. However, its strength parameters may vary significantly between different mines. The mean values of friction angle and cohesion were equal to 28° and 185kPa, while the standard deviations were 7° and 145kPa, respectively.

In many cases, results indicated specimens with highly diminished residual strength, indicating the weak zone's presence. This zone is characterised by a mean residual friction angle of 10° and a standard deviation of 2.6° , and its residual cohesion lies between 0kPa-5kPa. The mean value of soils' unit weight was 17 kN/m^3 , and its standard deviation 1.6 kN/m^3 .

2.2. Numerical Methods

2.2.1 Background information

The Finite Element Method (FEM) is primarily used in this work, being the most versatile and widely used numerical method in geotechnical engineering. FEM need to be combined with the Shear Strength Reduction (SSR) technique to perform ultimate limit state analysis. In the SSR type of analysis, herein based on the Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion, the safety factor is calculated by progressively reducing the shear strength of the material to bring the slope to the verge of failure.

A reference model was established with a 200m slope height, the maximum reported in the literature, and a slope inclination of 10° , a mild inclination for a high slope. The weak zone was

simulated as a 5m thick horizontal soil layer. For the overburden soil, the mean values of Theocharis et al. (2021) for the friction angle ($\phi=28^\circ$) and cohesion ($c=185\text{kPa}$) were used. The weak zone was assigned significantly reduced strength parameters with respect to the overburden material, presumed to be the zone's residual strength. Four residual friction angles of 5° , 8° , 12° and 15° were implemented, with its cohesion being 5kPa . Stiffness for the overburden soil and the weak zone is 50MPa ; however, this stiffness has a minor impact on slope stability. Additionally, the strength and stiffness of the bedrock do not affect the results. Poisson's ration, dilation angle and moist unit weight are $\nu=0.3$, $\psi=0^\circ$ and $\gamma=17\text{kN/m}^3$ respectively, for all materials. Typically, the dilation angle has a minor but systematic effect on the SF and the failure mechanism; less than 5% difference on SF between $\psi=\phi$ and $\psi=0^\circ$ (Liu et al. 2015; Tutluoglu et al. 2011). However, the flow rule has a significant impact on steep slopes (inclination angle more than 40°) of high friction angle materials (e.g. $\phi>40^\circ$) (Tschuchnigg et al. 2015a; 2015b). In the present work, a non-associated flow rule with $\psi=0^\circ$ has been employed as mild inclinations are considered, the friction angle is less than 35° , and the dilation's angle impact on the stability calculations would be minor. Last, the Mohr-Coulomb elastic-perfectly plastic constitutive model was employed. In summary, the geometrical and geotechnical parameters of the reference model are shown in Table 1.

Two-dimensional (2D) plane strain and drained conditions were used. Vertical boundaries were located at a $2H$ distance from the slope's crest and toe, respectively, and the horizontal bottom boundary at a distance H from the slope's toe to ensure the minimization of the boundary conditions effect, where H stands for the slope's overall height (Figure 1). A very fine discretisation was used for FEM, and mesh density was increased in some critical areas (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Geometry and main parameters for the reference model

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Reference value</i>	<i>Examined range</i>
Overburden's soil friction angle	ϕ ($^{\circ}$)	28	21 - 35
Overburden's soil cohesion	c (kPa)	185	40 - 185
Weak zone's (residual) friction angle	ϕ_z ($^{\circ}$)	10	5 - 15
Weak zone's (residual) cohesion	c_z (kPa)	5	5
Unit weight	γ (kN/m ³)	17	17
Stiffness	E (MPa)	50	50
Poisson ratio	ν	0.35	0.35
Dilation angle	ψ ($^{\circ}$)	0	0
Slope height	H (m)	200	50 - 200
Slope inclination	β ($^{\circ}$)	10	8 - 14
Weak zone's inclination	β_z ($^{\circ}$)	0	(-6) - (+6)
Weak zone's thickness	d_z (m)	5	0.5 - 5

* Positive β_z indicates a dip (inclination) towards the excavation, i.e. against stability.

Table 1. Geometrical and geotechnical parameters for the reference model and their typical range (based on data from Greek lignite mines)

Two widely available and popular software were used and compared to each other: Plaxis2D of Bentley and RS2 of Rocscience. In Plaxis2D, 6-node or 15-node triangular elements are

available, while in RS2, the selection is restricted to 3 and 6 nodes for triangular, and 4 and 8 nodes for rectangular elements. The limited number of nodes in RS2 may lead to inaccuracies, especially on initial stresses, the boundaries of the model, and high stress gradient areas. Furthermore, RS2 results varied more with mesh density and demanded caution in the discretisation and meshing procedures. Preliminary analyses showed that the simulation of a layer with a thickness of less than 2% of the slope's height might lead to inconsistent results in RS2. On the contrary, due to the higher number of nodes, Plaxis2D can accurately manage even a layer's thickness of 0.5% of the slope's height (results not presented herein). Nonetheless, note that the accurate layer's thickness is insignificant for the analysis, as will be shown in the next section.

Analyses in both FEM software were conducted for 6-noded triangular elements, similar mesh densities, and they were further validated with the 15-node triangular elements in Plaxis2D. All the reference model analyses presented identical failure mechanisms and SF values (differences less than 1%). Two indicative analysis results conducted with RS2 and Plaxis2D are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Failure surfaces and SF considering the reference case and $\phi_z=5^\circ$

Finally, it is noteworthy that in FEM, the weak zone can be simulated in two distinct ways: as a thin soil layer (layer-case) or as a "zero thickness" interface element (interface-case). The layer-case approach demands the determination of the weak zone's thickness that is unknown in practice. Besides, implementing layers with very small thickness compared to the overall geometry of the slope may lead to inconsistent mesh element sizes and computational problems. For the interface element, a reduction factor is typically applied to decrease the interface's strength with respect to the adjacent soil's parameters, and the use of an interface may cause numerical issues that sometimes demand case-specific solutions. For the scope of the present work, as the layer's thickness is considered a parameter under investigation, only the layer-case approach is implemented. However, it should be noted that preliminary analyses applying an interface element with similar strength parameters led to identical results (results not presented herein).

2.2.2 Finite elements versus limit equilibrium

In this section, FEM-SSR results are compared with results derived from the Limit Equilibrium Method (LEM) as a reference comparison for the weak zone soil profile. LEM leads the slope stability analysis over the last decades providing simplicity and speed in the calculation process. However, LEM does not consider the stress-strain relationship of the materials. Simultaneously, the need to assume or know in advance the shape and the location of the failure surface is necessary, mainly for non-circular failures as those of lignite mines. On the contrary, FEM does not require any assumption on the failure surface but identifies it based on soil's stress-strain response. Nonetheless, FEM demands higher computational time and a more detailed description of soil behaviour. The two FEM (Plaxis2D and RS2) software used in the previous section were compared with one LEM software (Slide2 by Rocscience) based on the stratigraphy of Figure 1. Comparison is based primarily on the SF and the failure surface.

For LEM analyses, Spencer's method was implemented, combined with the Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion. All LEM software demand the assumption of the shape (circular or non-circular) and, in some cases, also the location of the failure surface to provide reliable results, depending on the search method. Figure 4(a) and Figure 4(b) illustrate two LEM analyses (Slide2) for the reference case and $\phi_z=5^\circ$, assuming a non-circular and a circular type of failure surface, respectively. The two analyses provided different failure surfaces and SFs, even though the geometry and the geotechnical parameters of the materials are the same.

Figure 4. LEM results on identical models (reference case) using: (a) a non-circular and (b) a circular type failure surface

To simulate the complex failure mechanism and the non-circular failure surface, the block search method (Slide2) was employed. Various non-circular failure surfaces are employed that necessarily pass through a predefined area of the model. LEM results were practically identical to the FEM results for all cases examined (differences less than 2%).

1 2.3. The role of benches in the overall stability

2 A typical slope on surface mining consists of several benches, depending on the excavation
3 method and equipment used. The exact number and geometry of benches vary in a wide
4 range, making it difficult to study the slope's stability systematically. As a result, benches are
5 many times neglected without justification in slope stability analyses, even though the
6 consideration of a slope consisting of several benches is more realistic. In that vein, it is
7 essential to quantify the error for such an assumption.

8 Different slope geometries and benches' configurations were implemented for comparison in
9 Plaxis2D. The slope's geometrical parameters varied within their reported range (Table 1). The
10 reference parameters (Table 1, Reference values) describe the strength and stiffness of the
11 soils. Moreover, there is a need to assign a linear elastic material to the benches to avoid
12 minor regional bench failures, insignificant on the overall safety analysis. Under this
13 perspective, the weak zone was 1m thick to prevent regional failure surfaces at the benches
14 closest to the toe. As for the weak zone's strength, the comparison is conducted for residual
15 friction angles between 5° and 15°.

16 Different configurations were created with 1 to 9 benches and heights between 20m to 100m;
17 the bench face inclination varied from 12° to 45°, and the bench width from 100m to 200m.
18 The benches' number for each configuration depended on the geometry and the selected
19 range of the benches' parameters. The configurations' characteristics are summarised in Table
20 2. Overall, 21 different configurations were analysed, and Figure 5 shows two indicative
21 configurations.

22 Based on the results, the failure surface was similar among all models regardless of the
23 benches' number and geometry. Moreover, the models with benches provided higher SF
24 values in all cases, and the analysis without benches was always more conservative by 3%-

25 11%. Similarly to the present results, Verma et al. (2013) conducted FEM analyses for an
 26 internal dump in a coalfield in India and concluded that omitting benches was always more
 27 conservative with an SF error of 3-6%.

28

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Range</i>
Slope height, H (m)	50, 100, 150, 200
Slope inclination, β ($^{\circ}$)	8, 10, 12, 14
Weak zone's inclination, β_z ($^{\circ}$)	-6, -3, 0, 3, 6
Weak zone's friction angle, ϕ_z ($^{\circ}$)	5, 8, 12, 15
Number of benches	1 - 9
Bench height (m)	20 - 100
Bench width (m)	100 - 200
Bench face inclination ($^{\circ}$)	12 - 45

29 **Table 2.** Range of parameters for different configurations comparing slopes with and
 30 without benches

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32

33 **Figure 5.** Two indicative configurations for comparison of slopes with and without benches for
 34 H=200m and $\beta=10^{\circ}$

35

36 This work aims to systematically examine the influence of the weak zone on slope stability of
37 lignite mines, and one particular configuration with benches is not of interest. Thus, for the
38 analysis that follows, benches are ignored, noticing that the results are on the conservative
39 side and the error is less than 11%.

40 **3. Effect of geometry and geotechnical properties on slope stability**

41 In this section, the effect of the geometry and the geotechnical parameters on the Safety
42 Factor (SF) was investigated through the FEM (Plaxis2D). The critical parameters, as identified
43 in section 2, were investigated within their typical range in Greek lignite mines (Table 1).
44 Nonetheless, this particular range is rather broad, and lignite mines in other countries have
45 similar properties (e.g. Bednarczyk 2017; Ulusay et al. 2014). Each set of analysis was
46 conducted by varying one critical parameter, while the rest of the parameters kept their
47 reference values (see Table 1); the thickness of the weak zone was 1m.

48 FEM results indicate that the weak zone's friction angle is a key parameter to slope stability.
49 As shown in Figure 6, the weak zone's friction angle impact on the slope's stability is profound;
50 decreasing ϕ_z from 15° to 5° reduces SF between 45% to 58%, regardless of the weak zone's
51 inclination. The maximum reduction was encountered for the case of the steepest
52 unfavourable inclination of the weak zone ($\beta_z=6^\circ$), where SF drops from 2.00 to 0.85.
53 Furthermore, notice that even a small alteration of ϕ_z by 3° can change SF up to 30%; for
54 instance, for $\beta_z=6^\circ$ SF drops from 1.22 ($\phi_z=8^\circ$) to 0.85 ($\phi_z=5^\circ$).

55

56

57 **Figure 6.** SF versus weak zone's friction angle ϕ_z for different weak zone inclinations β_z

58

59 The tremendous effect of the weak zone on the SF is even more highlighted if the weak zone
60 is assigned strength parameters equal to the overburden soil's, i.e. $\phi_z=28^\circ$ and $c_z=185\text{kPa}$.
61 Then, the slope is essentially composed of one soil material and a bedrock formation, and for
62 the reference parameters, SF increases to 4.18. At the same time, the failure surface is almost
63 circular, with a small fraction being affected by the bedrock formation (Figure 7(b)). If the
64 bedrock is also considered to have the same properties as the soil, the SF drops slightly to
65 3.99, and the failure surface is circular (Figure 7(a)).

66 However, the weak zone's presence dictates a composite failure surface and a considerable
67 decrease of SF, from 4.18 to 2.47 ($\phi_z=15^\circ$), and 1.35 ($\phi_z=5^\circ$). Sliding occurs along the
68 horizontal/sub-horizontal weak zone and reaches the slope's top with a planar transition. For
69 lower weak zone's friction angles, the inclination of the planar transition gets steeper, and the
70 transition point gets closer to the crest (Figure 7(c) and (d)). Notice that the shear strains inside
71 the weak zone are very high but do not appear in Figures 7(c) or (d) due to the very small
72 thickness of the zone respecting the overall geometry (e.g. see the detail of Figure 7 (d)).

73 Both the strength and the inclination of the weak zone are critical parameters (Figure 6). On
74 the contrary, the effect of the weak zone's thickness was found insignificant, as shown in
75 Figure 8. Although d_z varies in a wide range of 0.5m-5m ($d_z/H=0.25\%-2.5\%$, for $H=200m$), the
76 difference in SF is minor, not exceeding 1.5%. Notice that for $d_z \leq 1m$, the required
77 computational time was remarkably higher.

78

79

80 **Figure 7.** Failure surface for (a) a homogeneous slope, (b) a slope with a bedrock formation
81 and no presence of a weak zone, (c) a slope with a weak zone of $\phi_z=15^\circ$, and (d) a slope with
82 a weak zone of $\phi_z=5^\circ$ considering the reference case

83

84 Design of slopes in surface mining is usually performed based on empirical safety factors
85 (deterministic approach). Nonetheless, safety factors do not accurately reflect the probability

86 of failure of a slope. Regardless of the type of geotechnical structure, safety factors not only
 87 tell little as to the possibility that a failure may occur, but they can even be misleading because
 88 of the ambiguity that exists between them and the underlying level of risk (Whitman 1984).
 89 For instance, large safety factors do not necessarily reflect a lower level of risk because the
 90 presence of considerable uncertainties can negate their effect. Probabilistic slope stability
 91 analysis offers the framework for addressing the above shortcoming by explicitly accounting
 92 for uncertainty sources in the computation of the probability of failure and its complement
 93 reliability (e.g. Obregon and Mitri 2019). This type of analysis greatly facilitates the use of
 94 reliability as a criterion of design optimization that plays a fundamental role in mining (Zevgolis
 95 et al. 2018).

96

97

98 **Figure 8.** SF versus weak zone's thickness d_z , for different weak zone's friction angles ϕ_z

99

100 In this work, Rosenbluth's point estimate method is employed to calculate the probability of
 101 failure and assess each parameter's importance on slope stability (Rosenblueth 1975). This
 102 method is widely used in geotechnical practice due to its simplicity and accuracy (Baecher and

103 Christian 2003). The low-order moments of the dependent random variable (herein the safety
104 factor) can be approximated based on the independent random variable's low-order
105 moments. Since the weak zone strength largely governs the slope's stability (see also Figure
106 6), its friction angle ϕ_z is considered as a random variable with mean value $\mu[\phi_z]=10^\circ$. Two
107 scenarios are considered in terms of the uncertainty of ϕ_z through two coefficient of variations
108 (COVs), i.e. $COV[\phi_z]=20\%$ and 30% . Both values are typical for friction angle and comply with
109 Zevgolis et al. (2021). Therefore, SF is a function of one independent variable; for comparison
110 purposes, SF is assumed to be both normally and lognormally distributed. Once the mean
111 value and standard deviation of SF are computed, the reliability index may also be computed
112 based on the point estimate method. Ultimately, the probability of failure can be assessed
113 through the normally distributed cumulative function of the reliability index.

114 Figure 9 shows the relation between P_F and SF for β_z varying between -6° and 6° . The Figure
115 clearly illustrates that SF, by itself, cannot reflect the risk level, given its highly non-linear
116 relation with P_F . This non-linear relation indicates that even a small decrease in SF might
117 significantly increase P_F and the corresponding risk level. For example, for the given range of
118 β_z , SF varies in a wide range, and results indicate that the slope is relatively stable in all cases
119 (minimum SF equals 1.45). Nonetheless, for $COV[\phi_z]=30\%$, a normally distributed SF with a
120 mean value equal to 1.45 corresponds to $P_F=9.9\%$, while an $SF=1.68$ corresponds to $P_F=2.3\%$.
121 For higher SFs, P_F is diminished, as for $SF= 2.42$, P_F equals 0.00005% . It is noteworthy that this
122 trend is more significant for a lognormally distributed SF and for $COV[\phi_z]=20\%$.

123 In the following sections, the significance of parameters ϕ , c , H , β and β_z on the probability of
124 failure (based on treating ϕ_z as a random variable) is parametrically evaluated. The equivalent
125 SFs for deterministic analysis (not presented) are always higher than 1. Results for
126 $COV[\phi_z]=30\%$ are always more conservative than for $COV[\phi_z]=20\%$. Besides, the normal
127 distribution typically provides more conservative results than the lognormal distribution, as

128 expected for low probabilities of failure, approximately less than 15% (Baecher and Christian
 129 2003). Because the two distributions lead to similar conclusions, the authors interpret Figures
 130 10-12, focusing only on the normal distribution results. Notice also that the vertical axes are
 131 in logarithmic scale (with a maximum value of 1, corresponding to 100%), as the calculated
 132 probabilities varied in a wide range. Calculated values of less than 0.00001% are omitted.

133

134

135 **Figure 9.** Probability of failure P_F versus SF, for varying weak zone's inclination β_z

136

137 Overburden soil's strength

138 The overburden soil's friction angle took the values 21°, 28° and 35° (i.e. the mean value plus
 139 and minus one standard deviation), while the cohesion 40kPa and 185kPa (i.e. the mean value
 140 minus one standard deviation) (Figure 10). In Figure 10(a), for $COV[\phi_z] = 30\%$, a friction angle
 141 increase from 21° to 35° reduces P_F from 2.4% to 0.3%; for $COV[\phi_z]=20\%$, reduces P_F from
 142 0.1% to 0.002%. In Figure 10(b), cohesion increases to 185kPa, and P_F varies between 0.7%
 143 and 0.06% for $COV[\phi_z]=30\%$, and between 0.009% and 0.00007% for $COV[\phi_z]=20\%$. The
 144 comparison between Figures 10(a) and (b) shows the influence of cohesion. Increasing

145 cohesion from 40kPa to 185kPa leads to a maximum P_F decrease for $\phi=21^\circ$, with P_F decreasing
 146 from 2.4% to 0.7% (for $COV[\phi_z]=30\%$), and from 0.1% to 0.009% (for $COV[\phi_z]=20\%$).

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148

149 **Figure 10.** P_F versus overburdens' soil friction angle ϕ , for (a) $c=40\text{kPa}$ and (b) $c=185\text{kPa}$

150

151 Slope's height and inclination

152 Figure 11 illustrates the effect of the slope's geometry on P_F . As expected, reducing the slope
 153 height reduces P_F (Figure 11(a)). This effect is more significant between $H=50\text{m}$ and 100m , as
 154 the curves are steeper in this area. For $COV[\phi_z]=30\%$, decreasing H from 200m to 100m
 155 reduces P_F from 0.2% to 0.03% , while decreasing H from 100m to 50m , reduces P_F from 0.03%
 156 to 0.0004% . It is noteworthy that the analysis considering for $COV[\phi_z]=20\%$ and a lognormal
 157 distribution for P_F is not presented herein, as all P_F were very low ($< 0.00001\%$).

158 Figure 11(b) presents an almost linear relation between P_F in log scale and β , with a 2° increase
 159 in the slope's inclination resulting in a P_F increase of approximately 50% , for $COV[\phi_z]=30\%$,
 160 and 80% , for $COV[\phi_z]=20\%$. Comparing the reference value ($\beta=10^\circ$) and a steeper slope of

161 $\beta=14^\circ$, P_F rises from 0.2% to 0.9%, for $\text{COV}[\phi_z]=30\%$, and from 0.001% to 0.02%, for
 162 $\text{COV}[\phi_z]=20\%$.

163

164

165 **Figure 11.** P_F versus (a) slope height H and (b) slope inclination β

166

167 Weak zone's inclination

168 Figure 12 illustrates the variance of P_F with β_z . Indicatively, for $\text{COV}[\phi_z]=30\%$ and $\beta_z=-6^\circ$ (a dip
 169 of strata in favour of stability), P_F equals 0.00005%, while the respective value for $\beta_z=6^\circ$ is 9.9%.
 170 The range of P_F is broader for the lognormal distribution, with P_F ranging from 7.5% to a value
 171 less than 0.00001%. In any case, the results indicate the critical role of the dip of the weak
 172 zone.

173 Figure 13 illustrates the shear strains and the failure surface for four indicative configurations
 174 with different geometric parameters; Figure 13(a) shows the reference model, and Figures
 175 13(b)-13(d) show characteristic results of the parametric analysis for different H , β and β_z . For
 176 the reference model ($H=200\text{m}$, $\beta=10^\circ$, and $\beta_z=0^\circ$) $\text{SF}=1.94$ for $\phi_z=10^\circ$, and $P_F=0.22\%$ for
 177 $\text{COV}[\phi_z]=30\%$ (Figure 13(a)). Considering slope height reduced by 50m, SF is increased by 4%

178 (SF=2.01), but the failure surface remains practically identical (Figure 13(b)). The respective P_F
 179 is reduced to 0.13% (41% decrease). The decrease of the slope's inclination β by 2° leads to an
 180 SF increase of 15% (SF=2.24) and a P_F decrease of 50% (0.11%), with the failure surface moving
 181 slightly to the left (Figure 13(c)). Last, in Figure 13(d), a slight deviation of the weak zone's
 182 inclination ($\beta_z=-3^\circ$) results in an SF rise of 13% (SF=2.19) but also in a huge decrease of P_F
 183 96% (0.008%). In this specific case, even if the effect of β on SF is marginally greater than the
 184 effect of β_z , their vast P_F difference indicates that β_z is crucial.

185

186

187 **Figure 12.** P_F versus weak zone's inclination β_z

188

189 All analyses present similar failure surfaces; they have a part in the weak zone and reach the
 190 ground surface with a planar transition of approximately 45° . Moreover, a reflection of the
 191 shear band that identifies the transition to the ground surface is always present. It is
 192 concluded that, for dry conditions, the most critical parameters are those of the weak zone,
 193 i.e. the weak zone's inclination and friction angle. Specifically, the uncertainty of the weak
 194 zone's strength, considered a random variable and investigated through two different COVs,

195 tremendously affects the P_F . For all simulations probability of failure changed almost one
 196 order of magnitude for large probabilities and more than that when P_F is low when this COV
 197 increase from 20% to 30%. Finally, it is noteworthy that the weak zone characteristics are also
 198 challenging to determine in practice, making them even more important for stability analysis.

199

200

201 **Figure 13.** Failure surface and calculated SF and P_F for (a) the reference case, (b) $H=150m$, (c)
 202 $\beta=8^\circ$ and (d) $\beta_z=-3^\circ$, considering $\mu[\phi_z]=10^\circ$ and $COV[\phi_z]=50\%$

203

204 4. The effect of water on slope stability

205 In this section, groundwater's influence is considered through pore water pressure using the
 206 simplified approach of r_u coefficient (Bishop and Morgenstern 1960). This method is

207 frequently used for slope stability in engineering practice, as the groundwater regime is often
208 difficult or impossible to identify.

209 The pore water pressure is calculated as:

$$210 \quad u = r_u(\gamma z) \quad (1)$$

211 where r_u is the coefficient of pore pressure (ranging from 0, i.e. zero pore pressure, to 1, i.e.
212 zero effective stress), γ is the soil unit weight, and z is the depth below the soil surface.
213 Furthermore, if the saturated soil unit weight is 20 kN/m^3 , and the water unit weight is 10
214 kN/m^3 , $r_u=0.5$ is equivalent to a phreatic water table lying at the soil surface.

215 The r_u method cannot be implemented in Plaxis2D, and thus, the analyses that follow were
216 carried out with RS2. Note that RS2 results for dry conditions ($r_u=0$) are practically identical
217 with the values derived from Plaxis2D. Different pore water pressures were simulated, using
218 r_u equal to 0 (dry conditions), 0.2 and 0.4, with the soil's moist unit weight presumed to be 17
219 kN/m^3 . It should be noted that all FEM analyses performed for $r_u=0.4$ and $\phi_z \leq 8^\circ$ led to SF values
220 less than or very close to 1.00.

221 Figures 14-16 illustrate the variance of P_F with the parameters ϕ , c , H , β and β_z , and for three
222 different r_u (considering $\mu[\phi_z]=10^\circ$ and $\text{COV}[\phi_z]=20/30\%$). The probability of failure was
223 computed considering SF as normally distributed. Increasing r_u results in a substantial P_F
224 increase as expected, with $r_u=0.4$ leading to immense probabilities of failure. For example, in
225 Figure 14(a), for the reference model ($\phi=28^\circ$) and $\text{COV}[\phi_z]=30\%$, increasing r_u from 0 to 0.4
226 increases P_F from 0.2% to 33.2%.

227 Extreme values for the P_F are encountered for the highest values of β and β_z . In Figure 15(b),
228 the combination of $\beta=14^\circ$ and $r_u=0.4$ results in $P_F=89.6\%$ ($\text{COV}[\phi_z]=20\%$), while in Figure 16,
229 $P_F=89.6\%$ for $\beta_z=6^\circ$. It is noteworthy that in these analyses, the mean values of the SF

230 distributions are less than 1 and almost identical to each other. In such cases, smaller COVs
 231 will provide larger probabilities of failure, as a greater part of the SF distribution is less than 1.
 232 For instance, for $COV[\phi_z]=30\%$, the respective results of P_F are smaller, as they equal 79.8%
 233 and 79.6% for $\beta=14^\circ$ and $\beta_z=6^\circ$, respectively.

234

235

236 **Figure 14.** P_F versus r_u coefficient for overburden soil's (a) friction angle ϕ and (b) cohesion c

237

238

239 **Figure 15.** P_F versus r_u coefficient for (a) slope's height H and (b) slope's inclination β

240

241

242 **Figure 16.** P_F versus r_u coefficient for weak zone's inclination angle β_z

243

244 6. Conclusions

245 In the present work, the slope stability of surface mines has been numerically investigated
 246 within a probabilistic framework. The focus was on the weak zone often encountered near
 247 the bottom of open-pit lignite and coal mines excavations. This weak zone leads to a type of
 248 failure common in such mines of several countries, such as Greece, Turkey, Poland, and
 249 Australia, while failure incidents related to a weak zone have been reported worldwide on
 250 various occasions. Several numerical issues on analysis and design were addressed, and the
 251 critical parameters of stability were identified and discussed. Their effect on SF was
 252 numerically quantified and evaluated, primarily through the FEM combined with SSR. The
 253 point estimate method was implemented to evaluate their significance through the
 254 probability of slope failure.

255 Initially, two FEM (Plaxis2D and RS2) and one LEM (Slide2) geotechnical software were
 256 implemented for comparison. A reference slope with a weak zone was simulated, and slope

257 stability results were identified as identical. An excellent agreement was demonstrated on the
258 failure mechanism, and the difference between the calculated SFs was less than 2%.

259 Moreover, slopes with benches, as typically in mines, and without benches, as typically in
260 slope stability analysis, were compared. Those without benches were found to provide similar
261 failure mechanisms and a marginally lower SF, compared to a slope consisting of benches and
262 equivalent geometrical characteristics. The comparison was conducted for 21 different
263 configurations, with the model's parameters, the number of benches, bench height, width and
264 bench face inclination varying in a wide range. The difference in SF in all cases does not exceed
265 11%. Thus, benches' influence can be ignored, noticing that the results are always on the safe
266 side.

267 Furthermore, the effect of geometrical and geotechnical parameters on slope stability was
268 examined. All analyses present similar failure surfaces with a part in the weak zone that reach
269 the ground surface with a transition of approximately 45°. FEM analyses, literature and
270 experience all agree that the most critical parameter is the weak zone's strength; decreasing
271 friction angle ϕ_z from 15° to 5° leads to an SF decrease between 45% to 58%, for the weak
272 zone's inclination ranging between 0°-6°, for the reference model. The point estimate method
273 was employed to calculate the probability of failure and assess each parameter's importance
274 on the slope stability, considering ϕ_z as a random variable since the weak zone strength largely
275 governs the slope's stability. The uncertainty of the weak zone's strength, investigated
276 through two different COVs, affects the P_F dramatically. For all simulations probability of
277 failure changed almost one order of magnitude for large probabilities and more than that
278 when P_F is low when COV increased from 20% to 30%. The inclination of the weak zone was
279 treated parametrically and is also crucial, as changing β_z from 0° to 6° resulted in a P_F increase
280 from 0.2% to 9.3%. Even more, the slight decrease in β_z from 0° to -3° resulted in a vast P_F
281 decrease of 96% (0.008%). Finally, the layer's thickness is insignificant for the overall stability.

282 The soil strength (friction angle and cohesion) of the overburden material and the height and
283 the inclination of the corresponding slope are essential in the safety analysis. The influence of
284 ϕ , c , H and β on the P_F is notable but not as crucial as the effect of β_z . In particular, P_F for the
285 reference case is 0.2%, and variations of their values increase P_F up to 2.4%. Moreover, it was
286 shown that small variations of their values might cause noticeable deviations to SF but do not
287 crucially affect P_F . As a result, it is concluded that the most critical parameters are those of the
288 weak zone, i.e. the weak zone's inclination and friction angle, and their influence in different
289 configurations was quantified. It is noteworthy that the weak zone characteristics are also
290 challenging to determine, making them even more critical for stability analysis.

291 Groundwater was considered through pore water pressure using the simplified approach of
292 r_u coefficient. Water pressure's effect is vital as P_F vastly increases with the increase of r_u . For
293 the reference model, r_u values of 0, 0.2 and 0.4 correspond to P_F 0.2%, 2.8% and 33.2%,
294 respectively. Although the value of $r_u=0.4$ might represent high pore pressures ($r_u=0.5$ is
295 equivalent to a phreatic water table lying at the soil surface), it further supports groundwater's
296 crucial role. The highest P_F s are encountered for the cases that parameters β and β_z were
297 increased with respect to the reference model to 14° and 6° respectively, as P_F equals 89.6%
298 in both cases and $r_u=0.4$. These vast increases of the P_F indicate that even very stable slopes
299 in dry conditions can reach failure if the pore water pressure increases. As a result,
300 groundwater conditions are identified as one of the most critical parameters on slope stability,
301 along with β_z and ϕ_z .

302 The present work has employed numerical analysis within a probabilistic framework to
303 systematically investigate the critical parameters' effect on slope stability. The crucial role of
304 the weak zone's strength and inclination was identified, and their effect on slope stability was
305 quantified through the probability of slope's failure. At the same time, the present work

306 included the groundwater pore pressures in a practical and standard way, quantifying the
307 crucial role of water on stability.

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312 **8. Conflict of interest**

313 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
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